

RESEARCH REPORT

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Mission Report: Vulture Tagging and Sampling. Sabie Game Park, Mozambique, August 2024.

PREPARED BY:

André Botha and Joice Cadmo Ussaca

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INTRODUCTION

TREPA (Threat Reduction for the Environment, People, and Animals) is a research project that aims to help fill knowledge gaps regarding the intersectionality of risks for zoonotic diseases of pandemic potential and wildlife use and trade with a One Health approach. TREPA is a 5-year project that started in September 2022. The TREPA team began collecting animal data in October 2023 and social science data in 2024. TREPA's 2024 work in Mozambique was funded and supported by the US National Science Foundation (CMMI: 2120065). This document serves as the mission report for the fieldwork activities focused on the trapping, fitting of tracking, and collection of samples from vultures in the Sabie Game Park, Mozambique in early August 2024.

The main objectives of the data collection activities were to establish a tracking sample of 10 vultures trapped in the Sabie Game Park, Mozambique, by fitting 65g Spoortrack Satellite tags to each bird using a back-pack harness made of Teflon. Trapped birds were also to be sampled for the presence of *B. anthracis* spores by means of swabs from the mouth, face, legs, and cloacal area of the bird and feather and blood samples were also collected for analysis according to the agreed protocol.

WORKPLAN

Data collection activities were conducted between August 1st - 3rd, 2024.

DETAILED AGENDA

Camera trapping

On July 20th, 2024, Mr. Botha traveled to Skukuza and collected 4 trail cameras and memory cards from Dr. Louis van Schalkwyk to be installed in Sabie Game Park (**SGP**). These cameras and cards were handed over to Dr. Gianluca Zaffarano in Hoedspruit on July 28th, 2024, and were delivered to Sabie Game Park the week after.

During tagging fieldwork, it was evident that the staff from Sabie Game Park were unsure about the approach and protocols to follow with regard to the use of the cameras. Following the TREPA group meeting on August 20th, 2024, Dr. Henriette van Heerden drafted a protocol that was shared with SGP staff. Unfortunately, no carcass has been located since to place the cameras at as yet.

Vulture tagging

Mr. Botha travelled from South Africa to SGP via the Ressano Garcia border post while Mr. Ussaca drove up from Maputo. Both arrived at SGP on the afternoon of July 31st, 2024. The team was met upon their arrival by Messrs Smit and Eni and they discussed plans and logistics with a view to start trapping the vultures on the reserve on the morning of August 1st.

Trapping started late on the morning of August 1st as it took SGP staff a while to source a suitable carcass that could be used as bait to trap the vultures. The team was however eventually able to set a trap at 11.10 at location 25.155269S 032.07179E using half of a Waterbuck *Kobus ellipsiprymnus* carcass, about 300m from the shore of the Corumane dam and, after moving away a suitable distance from the trapping site, but keeping it in our field of view, proceeded to wait and scan the sky for any large birds approaching the carcass.

There was little large bird movement in the vicinity of the carcass for the first few hours, but an adult female Bateleur *Terathopius ecaudatus* eventually landed at the carcass at 15:55. The team moved closer to the trap to obtain a better view at 16:05 and saw that an adult Tawny Eagle had also arrived unseen and was perched on a small snag about 15m away from the carcass. After a few minutes, noted that the Bateleur was trapped and proceeded to remove her from the trap for processing. The traps were re-set prior to the team moving some distance away to process the bird in hand. As the team had no suitable tracking to fit to the bird, she was only banded with an AFRING metal ring, and various biometric measurements were taken for the banding database.

Once the bird was released, the team continued their vigil for another hour, but no further activity was observed in the vicinity of the trapping site. The team eventually removed the traps and carcass, and returned to camp at 17.15 to prepare for trapping the next morning.

The next day, the team departed from camp just after 07.00 on the morning of August 2nd, following up on a report from rangers of vultures perched in trees on the central road in the reserve to the north of camp. Fortunately, there were still a fair number of vultures perched in the area reported and the team decided to set their traps about 250 meters from where the nearest birds were perched at 25.027572S 032.062695E. This was also the same location researchers used for trapping on August 3rd. The research team used the same carcass of the day before and did not have to wait long after retreating about 450m up the road before the first vultures descended and started feeding on the bait. Once the birds had started feeding, the team was able to move closer and, once they had confirmed that some birds were trapped, they moved in to secure them. Two African White-backed Vultures *Gyos africanus* (**AWBV**) were captured on the first feed.

The research team retreated about 150m away from the trapping and proceeded to process the birds by banding and fitting satellite tracking units to each. Each bird was also aged, weighed and other biometric measurements taken while Mr. Ussaca proceeded with the collection of relevant samples. The first two attempts at drawing blood from the tarsal vein of the birds were unsuccessful and it was decided to release these individuals without placing them under further

stress.

Once both birds were processed, the team returned to the trapping site and re-opened the traps in the hope of catching more birds. The researchers didn't have to wait very long before another two AWBV's were trapped and processed. This time, Mr. Ussaca achieved success in collecting blood from both birds without a problem and the team was able to release the last bird after 20 minutes in captivity, both departing with satellite tags on their backs.

The second trapping attempt unfortunately depleted the available food on site and the SGP team had to return to camp to collect the other half of the Waterbuck carcass. That provided an opportunity to observe and count the vultures present at the trapping site. The research team counted 63 AWBV's of varying ages, as many as 9 Hooded Vultures *Necrosyrtes monachus*, an adult pair of White-headed Vultures *Trigonoceps occipitalis* as well as at least 3 immature birds, and a single, immature Cape Vulture *Gyps coprotheres* at the feed.

Once the SGP team returned, the team re-baited the traps but had to wait a little longer this time for the birds to return to feed. This happened at approximately 14.40 and the team managed to trap a further two AWBV's who were duly tagged, processed, and sampled before release, bringing the deployed tagging sample to a total of six birds for the day, all being AWBV's. As the bait was almost fully depleted, the team agreed to source a fresh bait and attempt further trapping the next day, therefore returning to camp at 16.15.

Weather conditions changed overnight and, when the team returned to the trapping site, it was much cooler on the morning of August 3rd than the previous day and there were far fewer birds perched in the trees at the site. However, the research team also noticed 3 Lappet-faced Vultures *Torgos tracheliotus* perched in the vicinity who likely were feeding on the remains of the Waterbuck carcass the day before. There was however no sign of any remains left on the trapping site and the large number of hyena spoor was a rather definitive clue as to whom removed what was left of the carcass overnight.

SGP staff kindly sourced a fresh Impala carcass which the team secured to the ground and placed

the traps around at 07:20 on the morning of August 3rd. This time, there was a much longer wait and the team needed to retreat even further away from the trapping site before the birds started arriving in good numbers. The first active feeding was observed at 09.35 and the team trapped the first two AWBV's by 09.40. The birds were duly tagged, processed, and sampled, after which they were released.

More bait was added to the trapping site and the birds returned within a few minutes. The SGP team returned to the trapping site while the rest of the team prepared the processing sampling table. This time, a sub-adult White-headed Vulture was caught, but she sadly escaped from the trap before the SGP staff could secure her. The team retreated again barely 250m from the trapping site when the birds returned a third time and the team managed to trap, band, tag, and process another two ABWV's which completed our tracking sample and target of ten tagged vultures.

The traps were removed, the research team returned back to camp at 12.30 and the vultures were allowed to consume what remained of the carcass once everyone had withdrawn from the site. Mr. Botha returned to the trapping site at 15.30 and there was nothing left of the carcass and no signs of vultures in the area. At least three immature Bateleur were however perched in trees near the scene.

Mr. Botha returned to South Africa via Ressano Garcia on the morning of August 4th and Mr. Ussaca returned to Maputo to deposit the collected samples to the Eduardo Mondlane Biotechnology Center laboratory for processing.

Table 1. Summary of the bird tagged and fitted with rings at Sabie Game Park, August 1-3, 2024.08.26

Ring	Date	Species	Name	Age	Sex	PTT no	Manufacturer
9A41231	2024-08-01	151	Bateleur	4	2		
MM01086	2024-08-02	107	White-backed Vulture	3	0	1438	Spoortrack
MM01087	2024-08-02	107	White-backed Vulture	3	0	1439	Spoortrack
MM01088	2024-08-02	107	White-backed Vulture	4	0	1441	Spoortrack
MM01089	2024-08-02	107	White-backed Vulture	3	0	1486	Spoortrack

MM01090	2024-08-02	107	White-backed Vulture	3	0	1487	Spoortrack
MM01091	2024-08-02	107	White-backed Vulture	4	0	1488	Spoortrack
MM01092	2024-08-03	107	White-backed Vulture	4	0	1489	Spoortrack
MM01093	2024-08-03	107	White-backed Vulture	3	0	1490	Spoortrack
MM01094	2024-08-03	107	White-backed Vulture	3	0	1491	Spoortrack
MM01095	2024-08-03	107	White-backed Vulture	4	0	1495	Spoortrack

There were a few positives from the field trip which can be summarized as follows:

- Mr. Ussaca successfully managed to collect blood from 8 vultures after initially finding the process difficult, thus knowledge transfer and capacity building were cornerstones for this fieldwork trip. He should have a lot of confidence in doing this in the future.
- The staff from SGP were really very supportive and participated fully in the trapping effort, quickly learning how to extract and safely handle and monitor the welfare of the birds during processing.
- It was encouraging to see as many as 60-70 vultures at feeding sites and to record 5 different species of vultures over the two days of successful trapping. SGP certainly lends itself to more work of this nature in future and the research team is in a good position to expand on the Mozambique sample of tagged vultures for the TREPA project on this site, resources permitting.

REFERENCES

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EWT Protocol - Standard Operating Procedure for BOPP: Catching, handling and sampling birds. 2022.

African White-backed-, White-headed and Hooded Vultures feeding at our trapping site in the Sabie Game Park, Mozambique.

Taking biometric measurements from the female Bateleur we trapped on August 1st.

Mr. Joice Ussaca (left) preparing the sampling equipment while Mr. Hanro Smit and Mr. Kid Glorio Eni are holding the African White-backed Vulture that has already been fitted with a satellite tag.

Sabie Game Park staff with Mr. Joice Ussaca after successful trapping on Day 2.